

An Evidence-Theoretic Framework for Online Learning from Expert Advice

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3 Proofs

3.1 Learning from Expert Advice Algorithms as Restricted Evidential Reasoning

Algorithm 1 Evidential reasoning protocol for the Halving algorithm

For each $h \in \mathcal{H}$, $m^1(\{h\}) = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{H}|}$

for $t \in \{1, \dots, T\}$ **do**

Receive x

Compute $m^{\mathcal{H} \downarrow x Y}$, restriction of m^t

Predict $y' = \arg \max_{y \in \{0,1\}} m^{\mathcal{H} \downarrow x \{0,1\}}(y)$

Receive y and construct $m^y = \begin{cases} 1 & \{h \in \mathcal{H} : h(x) = y\} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$

Penalize learner based on $l_{0-1}(y, y')$

$w = m^{\mathcal{H} \downarrow x Y} \oplus m^y$

Compute $w^{Y \uparrow \mathcal{H}}$

$m^{t+1} = \text{Bet}(w)$

end for

Halving

Theorem 3.1. Let $l_{0-1}(y, y') = \mathbb{1}_{y \neq y'}$ be the 0 – 1 loss function. Then, Algorithm 1 is equivalent to the Halving algorithm: in particular, the two algorithms always make the same predictions. Consequently, in the realizable setting, Algorithm 1 enjoys a regret smaller than $\log_2(|\mathcal{H}|)$.

Proof. The Halving algorithm is obtain from Algorithm 1 by setting the learner A as in Algorithm 2.

Assume that Algorithms 1 and 1 are executed based on a common stream of data $\{(x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_T, y_T)\}$. We prove the result by showing, by induction, that at each time-step t , $m^t(\{h\}) > 0$ if and only if $h \in C^t$. At the beginning of the stream, $C = \mathcal{H}$ and $m(\{h\}) = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{H}|} > 0$, so the above condition holds. Let t be arbitrary and assume the above condition holds for all $t' \leq t$. Then, $m^{\mathcal{H} \downarrow x \{0,1\}}\{y\} = \sum_{h \in C^t} m^t(\{h\})$ and, consequently, the prediction provided by Algorithm 1 at time step t is equivalent to the y' returned by the learner in Algorithm 2. Afterwards, w will

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Algorithm 2 Learner for the Halving algorithm.

$C = \mathcal{H}$

$t = 1$

for $(x, y) \in z$ **do**

$C^t = \{h \in C : h(x) = y\}$

end for

$x = z[-1]$

Return $y' = \arg \max_{y \in \{0,1\}} |\{h \in C^t : h(x) = y\}|$

be defined by $w(A) = \begin{cases} 1 & A = \{h \in C^t : h(x) = y\} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$ and, consequently,

$m^{t+1}(\{h\}) = \frac{1}{|\{h \in C^t : h(x) = y\}|}$. Note, in particular, that $m^{t+1}(\{h\}) > 0$ if and only if $h \in C^{t+1}$ as defined in Algorithm 2 when $z = [(x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_t, y_t)]$. The result follows by induction. Finally, the bound on the regret of Algorithm 1 directly follows by the proved equivalence and the fact that the regret of the Halving algorithm is upper bounded by $\log_2(|\mathcal{H}|)$ □

Algorithm 3 Evidential reasoning protocol for the Weighted Majority algorithm

Set $m^1(\mathcal{H}) = 1$

Set $\eta \leq \sqrt{\frac{2 \log(|\mathcal{H}|)}{T}}$

for $t \in \{1, \dots, T\}$ **do**

Receive x

Compute t^m , plausibility transform of m^t

Select $h \in \mathcal{H}$ randomly according to t^m and predict $y' = h(x)$

Receive y

Penalize learner based on $l(y, y')$

Construct $m^y(A) = \begin{cases} s = e^{-\eta} & A = \mathcal{H} \\ 1 - s & A = \{h \in \mathcal{H} : h(x) = y\} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$

$m^{t+1} = m^t \oplus m^y$

end for

Weighted Majority

Theorem 3.2. Assume that the loss function l satisfies $l(y, y') \in [0, 1]$, for any $y, y' \in Y$. Then, Algorithm 3 is equivalent to the

Weighted Majority algorithm, in the sense that, at each time step $t = \{1, \dots, T\}$, the two algorithms will select a prediction $y' \in \{0, 1\}$ according to the same probability distribution. Consequently, Algorithm 3 enjoys a regret bound of $\sqrt{2 \log(|\mathcal{H}|)T}$.

Proof. The Weighted Majority algorithm is obtained from Algorithm 1 by setting the learner A as in Algorithm 4.

Algorithm 4 Learner for the Weighted Majority algorithm.

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Set  $\eta = \sqrt{\frac{2 \log(|\mathcal{H}|)}{T}}$ 
For each  $h \in \mathcal{H}$ ,  $w(h) = 1$ 
for  $(x, y) \in z$  do
  for  $h \in \mathcal{H}$  do
     $w(h) = w(h)e^{-\eta \mathbb{1}_{h(x) \neq y}}$ 
  end for
end for
For each  $h \in \mathcal{H}$ ,  $w(h) = \frac{w(h)}{\sum_{h \in \mathcal{H}} w(h)}$ 
 $x = z[-1]$ 
Select  $h \in \mathcal{H}$  randomly according to  $w$ 
Return  $y' = h(x)$ 

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Assume that Algorithms 1 and 3 are executed based on a common stream of data $\{(x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_T, y_T)\}$: we will prove their equivalence by induction, similarly as in Theorem 3.1. Let $t = 1$. Then $pl_{m^1}(h) = 1$, for each $h \in \mathcal{H}$ and $t^m(h) = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{H}} = w(h)$, where w is the probability distribution over \mathcal{H} defined by Algorithm 4 when $z = [x]$. So, the equivalence holds at $t = 1$. Then, at time step t and assuming the above condition holds for every $t' \leq t$, Algorithms 1, using Algorithm 4 as learner, and 3 define the same probability distribution over experts, and, hence, the same probability distribution over predictions. After the update, it holds that $pl_{m^{t+1}}(h) = \begin{cases} pl_{m^t}(h) & h(x_t) = y_t \\ pl_{m^t}(h)s & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$, and $t^m(h) = \frac{pl_{m^{t+1}}(h)}{\sum_{h \in \mathcal{H}} pl_{m^{t+1}}(h)} = w^{t+1}(h)$, where w^{t+1} is the set of weights over \mathcal{H} defined by Algorithm 4. The result follows by induction. Finally, the regret bound for Algorithm 3 directly derives from the regret bound of the Weighted Majority algorithm. \square

3.2 Novel Learning from Expert Advice Algorithms Inspired by Evidential Reasoning

Evidential Halving

Theorem 3.3. *Assume realizability, and that*

$$l_\alpha(y, A) = \begin{cases} \alpha & A = \{0, 1\} \\ 0 & A = \{y\} \\ 1 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

with $\alpha < 1$. Then, Algorithm 5 enjoys a regret bound of $\text{Regret} \leq \frac{\log(|\mathcal{H}|)}{\log(\frac{1}{1-\beta})} + \frac{\alpha \log(|\mathcal{H}|)}{\log(\frac{1}{\beta})}$. For any $\alpha \leq 0.08$ there exists $\beta \in (0.6, 1)$ such that the above bound is smaller (up to logarithmic terms) than the minimum possible regret obtained by any (non-cautious) LEA algorithm. In particular, this holds for the Halving algorithm.

Proof. Let t be any time step and let $H^t = \bigcup_{A \in \mathcal{F}(m^t)} A$.

Assume that Algorithm 5 makes an error: then, at least $\beta \geq \frac{1}{2}$ experts in H^t made an error: hence, by definition of m^{t+1} , it holds that $|H^{t+1}| \leq (1 - \beta)|H^t|$. By induction, letting M be number

Algorithm 5 Evidential Halving

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 $m^1(\mathcal{H}) = 1$ 
for  $t \in \{1, \dots, T\}$  do
  Receive  $x$ 
   $w = \text{Bet}(m^t) \downarrow_x Y$ 
   $q = \arg \max_{y \in \{0, 1\}} w(\{y\})$ 
   $s = \max_{y \in \{0, 1\}} w(\{y\})$ 
   $m_p(A) = \begin{cases} \mathbb{1}_{s \geq \beta} & A = \{q\} \\ \mathbb{1}_{s < \beta} & A = \{0, 1\} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$ 
  Predict  $y' = \arg \max_{A \in \mathcal{F}(m_p)} m_p(A)$ 
  Receive  $y$  and construct  $m^y = \begin{cases} 1 & \{h \in \mathcal{H} : h(x) = y\} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$ 
  Penalize learner based on  $l_\alpha(y, y')$ 
   $m^{t+1} = m^t \oplus m^y$ 
end for

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of errors made by Algorithm 5 and assuming realizability, it follows that $1 \leq |H^T| \leq (1 - \beta)^M |\mathcal{H}|$ and hence $M \leq \frac{\log(|\mathcal{H}|)}{\log(\frac{1}{1-\beta})}$.

Conversely, assume that Algorithm 5 abstains (i.e., $y' = \perp$): then, at least $1 - \beta$ (and at most $\frac{1}{2}$) experts in H^t made an error: hence, by definition of m^{t+1} , it holds that $|H^{t+1}| \leq \beta |H^t|$. By induction, letting A be number of abstentions made by Algorithm 5, it follows that $1 \leq |H^T| \leq \beta^A |\mathcal{H}|$ and hence $A \leq \frac{\log(|\mathcal{H}|)}{\log(\frac{1}{\beta})}$. Thus, the result follows by summing the upper bounds for A and M . The second part of the result follows by numeric inspection of the regret bound. \square

Theorem 3.3 shows that when the cost associated with an abstention is small, Evidential Halving can obtain better performance (up to logarithmic terms) than any non-cautious LEA algorithm. In particular, if $\alpha \rightarrow 0$, setting $\beta = 1$, would provide an algorithm that never makes an error (as Algorithm 5 would make a prediction only when all experts agree which, under realizability, ensures that the prediction must be correct) but can abstain up to $|\mathcal{H}| - 1$ times: hence, this setting makes Evidential Halving equivalent to a cautious version of the classical Consistent algorithm [2].

Algorithm 6 Evidential reasoning protocol for the Evidential Weighted Majority algorithm

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For each  $h \in \mathcal{H}$ , set  $w^1(\mathcal{H}) = 1$ 
Set  $\eta \in (0.02, \ln(2)]$ 
for  $t \in \{1, \dots, T\}$  do
  Receive  $x$ 
  Select  $\emptyset \neq H \subseteq \mathcal{H}$  randomly according to  $m^t(H) = \frac{w^t(H)}{1 - w^t(\emptyset)}$ 
  Predict  $y' = H(x)$ 
  Receive  $y$ 
  Penalize learner based on  $l(y, y')$ 
  Construct  $m^y(A) = \begin{cases} s = e^{-\eta} & A = \mathcal{H} \\ 1 - s & A = \{h \in \mathcal{H} : h(x) = y\} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$ 
   $w^{t+1} = w^t \oplus m^y$ 
end for

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Evidential Weighted Majority

Theorem 3.4. *Assume that $l(y, y') \in [0, 1]$ for any $y \in Y, y' \subseteq Y$ and, furthermore $l(y, \{0, 1\}) \leq l(y, y')$ whenever $y' \neq \{y\}$. Then,*

Algorithm 6, with $\eta \in (0.2, \ln(2)]$, satisfies the following regret bound: □

$$\sum_{t=1}^T \langle m^t, l(y_t, m^t) \rangle - \min_{h \in \mathcal{H}} \sum_{t=1}^{T+1} v_h^t < \frac{T}{2} \left(\frac{1 - e^{-\eta}}{2\eta} + \eta \right), \quad (1)$$

where $l(y_t, \mathcal{H}) = (l(y_t, A(x_t)))_{A \subseteq \mathcal{H}}$. For \mathcal{H} sufficiently large, the above bound is smaller than the regret bound obtained by any (non-cautious) LEA algorithm achieving a bound of the form $C\sqrt{T \log |\mathcal{H}|}$. In particular, this holds for Weighted Majority.

Proof. Let $Z_t = \sum_{\emptyset \neq A \subseteq \mathcal{H}} w_t(A)$. Given $A \subseteq \Omega$, either A was in $\mathcal{F}(m^t)$ or not. In the first case, $w^{t+1}(A) = w_t e^{-\eta \mathbb{1}_{A(x) \neq y}}$, while in the second case there exists $B \in \mathcal{F}(m^t)$ such that $w^{t+1}(A) = (1-s)w^t$. Thus, it holds that $\log \frac{Z_{t+1}}{Z_t} \leq \log \left(\sum_{\emptyset \neq A \subseteq \mathcal{H}} \frac{w_t(A) e^{-\eta \mathbb{1}_{A(x) \neq y}}}{Z_t} + \sum_{\emptyset \neq A \subseteq \mathcal{H}} \frac{w_t(A)}{Z_t} (1-s) \right) = \log \left(\sum_{\emptyset \neq A \subseteq \mathcal{H}} m^t(A) e^{-\eta \mathbb{1}_{A(x) \neq y}} + \sum_{\emptyset \neq A \subseteq \mathcal{H}} m^t(A) (1-s) \right)$. Since, for all $a \in (0, 1)$ it holds that $e^{-a} \leq 1 - a + \frac{a^2}{2}$, by requiring that $\eta \in (0, 1)$, the above can be upper bounded by $\log \left(\sum_{\emptyset \neq A \subseteq \mathcal{H}} m^t(A) (1 - \eta \mathbb{1}_{A(x) \neq y} + \frac{(\eta \mathbb{1}_{A(x) \neq y})^2}{2} + 1 - s) \right) = \log \left(1 - \sum_{\emptyset \neq A \subseteq \mathcal{H}} m^t(A) (s - 1 + \eta \mathbb{1}_{A(x) \neq y} - \frac{(\eta \mathbb{1}_{A(x) \neq y})^2}{2}) \right)$.

Let $v_A^t = \mathbb{1}_{A(x_t) \neq y_t}$, $b_A = 1 - e^{-\eta} - \eta v_A^t + \eta^2 v_A^t / 2$. Since for every $\eta > 0$ it holds that $b_A \geq 0$, by [1], Prop. 1, we can upper bound the above as $\sum_{\emptyset \neq A \subseteq \mathcal{H}} m^t(A) \left(\frac{\pi}{\sqrt{b_A+1}} + \frac{(4+\pi)b_A}{2\sqrt{b_A+1}} - \frac{2(b_A+2) \arctan(\sqrt{b_A+1})}{\sqrt{b_A+1}} \right)$. Furthermore, for every $\eta < 1$, it holds that $b_A \leq 1$ and $b_A + 1 \geq 1$, hence $\frac{2(b_A+2) \arctan(\sqrt{b_A+1})}{\sqrt{b_A+1}} \geq \pi$ from which it follows that $\log \frac{Z_{t+1}}{Z_t}$ can be upper bounded by $\frac{(4+\pi)(1-e^{-\eta})}{2} - \frac{(4+\pi)\eta \langle m^t, v_A^t \rangle}{2} + \frac{(4+\pi)\eta^2}{4}$. Summing over all t we obtain that $\log \frac{Z_{T+1}}{Z_1}$ can be upper bounded by:

$$\frac{T(4+\pi)(1-e^{-\eta})}{2} + \frac{T(4+\pi)\eta^2}{4} - \eta \frac{4+\pi}{2} \sum_{t=1}^T \langle m^t, v^t \rangle \quad (2)$$

Note that $\log Z_1 = 0$. It is easy to show that, in the worst case, at time step t the result of $w^t \oplus m^y$, any subset A of \mathcal{H} , different from \emptyset , will have $w^t(A)$ equal to at least $(1-s)^p s^q$, where $p+q = \sum_{i=1}^t v_A^i$. Hence, $\log Z_{T+1} \geq \max_{\emptyset \neq A \subseteq \mathcal{H}} p \log(1-s) + q \log s$: assuming $s > 1-s$, and hence $\eta \leq \ln 2$, the previous quantity is larger than $\sum_{t=1}^{T+1} v_A^t \log(1-s)$. Hence, by [1], Prop. 2, $\log Z_{T+1} \geq \max_{\emptyset \neq A \subseteq \mathcal{H}} f(\eta) \sum_{t=1}^{T+1} v_A^t$, where $f(\eta) = \pi - \frac{4+\pi}{2} e^{-\eta} - 2(2 - e^{-\eta}) \arctan \sqrt{1 - e^{-\eta}}$ and, since for all $0.02 < \eta \leq \ln(2)$ it holds that $f(\eta) \geq -\eta \frac{4+\pi}{2}$, we have $\log Z_{T+1} \geq -\eta \frac{4+\pi}{2} \min_{\emptyset \neq A \subseteq \mathcal{H}} \sum_{t=1}^{T+1} v_A^t$. Thus, we obtain:

$$\sum_{t=1}^T \langle m^t, v^t \rangle - \min_{\emptyset \neq A \subseteq \mathcal{H}} \sum_{t=1}^{T+1} v_A^t \leq T \left(\frac{1 - e^{-\eta}}{\eta} + \frac{\eta}{2} \right). \quad (3)$$

Consequently, since $\alpha < 1$, and $\forall h \in \mathcal{H}, \{h\} \in \{A \subseteq \mathcal{H} : A \neq \emptyset\}$, we obtain the result.

For the second part of the result, as long as $|\mathcal{H}| \geq e^{T \left(\frac{1-e^{-\eta}}{2\eta} + \eta \right)^2}$, it holds that Algorithm 6 enjoys a smaller regret bound than any LEA algorithm, which is lower bounded by $\sqrt{T \log(|\mathcal{H}|)}$.

References

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